

Statistics in Litigation, Two Tax Court Case Studies

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Abstract:

This paper explores how statistics, tax law, and litigation interact while analyzing statistical considerations of two Tax Court cases that focus on the Research Tax Credit (RTC). The discussion also highlights how statistical methods are applied within IRS Revenue Procedure frameworks to estimate Qualifying Research Expenditures (QREs), the usual audit process when statistical methods are used, and the departure that the IRS took in the two cases. Finally, an overview is provided of recent changes to the Form 6765 for the RTC reporting requirements as it relates to statistical sampling.

Statistical sampling is a crucial tool for taxpayers claiming the RTC and the IRS auditing QREs, especially in situations when reviewing every potentially qualifying expense individually is impractical for either party.

Key Words: Survey Sampling, Litigation, Research and Development, RTC, Tax

Background:

Most developed countries offer tax benefits to promote Research and Development (R&D) investment. However, as shown below, companies in the United States recoup a lower proportion of their R&D spending through tax incentives compared to other developed nations.

Figure 1: Percent or R&D Expenditure Recovered through Tax Incentives

While actual percentages may vary depending upon facts and circumstances, and there are some countries with caps on the amounts of R&D expenditures recouped through tax incentives, the figure above compares the top percentages of R&D expenditures recovered for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) throughout the world. For example, to stimulate research and maintain a

competitive edge, Singapore pays SMEs 400% of their R&D expenditures, while the US credits approximately 10% of expenditures.^{i,ii,iii}

In general, the US RTC only provides a reduction in tax for companies who increase their domestic expenditures over prior years for R&D activities. The qualifying activities generally includes the design, development or improvement of products, processes, computer software, techniques, formulas or inventions.

Further, the Congress developed a four-part test to determine whether expenditures qualify for the RTC that centers around the concept of a “business component” which is defined as “any product, process, computer software, technique, formula, or invention that is intended to be held for sale, lease, or license, or used by the taxpayer in its trade or business.”

To determine eligibility, taxpayers must evaluate their research activities performed at the business component level using each of the four criteria below:

- 1) Permitted Purpose: The activity must be undertaken for the purpose of developing a new or improved business component and the improvement must relate to its function, performance, reliability, or quality.
- 2) Technological in Nature: The research must rely on principles of physical or biological sciences, engineering, or computer science.
- 3) Elimination of Uncertainty: There must be technical uncertainty at the outset regarding the capability, methodology, or appropriateness of design.
- 4) Process of Experimentation: Use systematic processes of evaluating alternatives to eliminate technical uncertainty.

The documentation requirements for the four-part test can be burdensome and taxpayers may have hundreds or even thousands of potentially qualifying business components to evaluate and substantiate. Therefore, the use statistical sampling to estimate qualifying expenditures for tax purposes is appealing – both for the taxpayer and the IRS. The taxpayer reduces time, money and effort documenting their business components and the IRS Exam teams have less to review in audit. Over the decades, the IRS has issued revenue procedures and field directives with guidance for statistical methods to establish its expectations of sound statistical practices.^{iv, v}

Statistical Sampling in RTC

Sampling is an efficient way to estimate QREs while reducing the burden of examining every business component. Without it, many taxpayers would find their credit of up to 10% of their expenditures would not outweigh the level of effort in documenting the four-part test in their cost/benefit analysis. Under IRS Revenue Procedure 2011-42, taxpayers may use sampling methods to extrapolate results up to their sampling frame when the work to conduct analysis on the entire sampling frame is onerous and there isn't better probative information available.^{vi} The revenue procedures specify specific documentation requirements that are standard expectations of any professionally conducted sample and estimation study. IRS auditors also expect statistical methods to maintain a nexus between sampling units and business components in the analysis.

The sampling and estimation process is like most survey sampling methods:

1. Define scope.

This includes the identification of any required sub-estimates to estimate QREs.

2. Construct a sample frame.

The most common sample frame is a list of potentially qualifying expenditures organized by project/contract or employee, but there are several ways to organize the expenditures into a logistically convenient data frame. The available data from administrative records may determine the sampling unit.

3. Determine the sampling unit.

While the sampling unit can be at the business component level, that is often not the case. The sample units do not necessarily correspond to a one-to-one relationship with a business component. They can be one to many, many to one, one to pieces of many, many to pieces to one, ... Whichever way the expenditures are combined or sliced to be listed on the sampling frame, the IRS expects the nexus between sampling units and business components to be clear – at least in the sample selections.

4. Design and draw the sample.

Stratified sampling based on the size of the sampling unit, as measured by expenditures or variables related to expenditures, is the most common sample design. The sample selection must be performed in a manner that can be reproduced upon audit.

5. Determine the required information for each sampled unit.

The arduous four-part test is performed and documented. The qualifying amount is determined for the units that meet the four-part test which is not necessarily the total expenditures.

6. Extrapolate the sample up to the entire sample frame.

Annual QRE estimates are needed for the RTC because credit is incremental in nature. Taxpayers must prove they paid or incurred more in R&D, or in some cases the same, compared to prior years. The IRS Revenue Procedure 2011-42 lists four possible design-based estimation techniques dating pre-World War II. These are: the Horvitz–Thompson estimator (more commonly known as the Mean Per Unit (MPU) estimator), the Difference estimator (where the non-qualifying expenditures are extrapolated and subtracted from the total expenditures to arrive at QREs), the combined ratio estimator, and the combined regression estimator. Separate ratio and regression estimators are not among the four in the revenue procedure due to concerns of potential cumulative bias when summing estimates over strata.

Using one of the four estimation methods from the IRS Revenue Procedure 2011-42 can be considered a safe harbor approach. However, the revenue procedure does allow for more modern estimation methods to be applied. When a taxpayer chooses a more advanced method of extrapolation, one of the IRS Statistical Sampling Coordinators must assess the merits of the statistical estimation performed because the IRS Computer Audit Specialists, who typically audit taxpayer samples, are not trained to assess estimation techniques beyond the four methods listed in the revenue procedure.

7. Document the process.

The IRS Revenue Procedure 2011-42 has two appendices with documentation requirements that are standard for any reputable statistical study.

IRS Audits of QREs Estimated from Statistical Samples

When taxpayers who use statistical samples to estimate values for their tax returns are selected for audit, IRS Exam team will ask for the sample method documentation, sample frame dataset, and the

sample dataset including the results of the tax determinations. Exam will also ask for the documentation supporting the tax decisions of qualifying amounts which may include substantiation of the four-part test for each criteria in the case of an estimate used to extrapolate the RTC. The IRS Exam team then checks whether the sampling units were selected according to a random number generator, determines whether they can reproduce the random selections, reviews the sample documentation, verifies the calculations and statistical decisions behind the extrapolated amounts, and reviews the supporting documentation of QREs found among the sampled units. Usually, statistical methods are not an issue during audit when taxpayers use knowledgeable statisticians to perform the work.

However, even when the IRS finds no statistical deficiencies, tax experts may still argue over minute details in tax issues regarding what and how much qualifies as QREs in the sampled selections. Results are re-extrapolated if QRE quantities in the sampled units are adjusted because of the audit.

This summarizes the typical approach for audits of RTC claims using statistical sampling. Whereas the following two Tax Court cases illustrate instances where the audits appear to not have followed this general approach.

[Phoenix Design Group, Inc., Petitioner v. Commissioner of Internal Revenue, Respondent](#)

Phoenix Design Group (PDG), an engineering and consulting firm in Nashville, Tennessee, hired Alliantgroup LP to calculate research credits for 409 projects from tax years 2013–2016. Alliantgroup excluded small projects, leaving 238 eligible for the credit, and selected a sample of 24 of these eligible projects. Of these, 20 qualified for the credit, leading to an estimated \$562,798 in credits over 2013–2016, with \$535,455 claimed on tax returns from 2015–2019.

The IRS audited the RTC of Tax Years 2015-2019 and on December 14, 2021, because of the audit, the IRS issued a notice of deficiency that:

- 1) disallowed most of the tax credit, to the amount of \$461,741, and
- 2) assessed penalties of \$91,807.

⇒ It is not clear from the court documents why the IRS disallowed nearly all the credit.

In March 2022, PDG petitioned the Tax Court to redetermine the deficiencies.

A year later in March of 2023, in preparation for the trial during an informal discovery process, the IRS requested documentation on the 20 projects that PDG deemed qualified.

⇒ It is also unclear why the IRS did not already have this documentation as they typically would have requested and received it during the audit.

PDG provided the documentation piecemeal from April through June of 2023.

⇒ It is not understood why PDG took the extended time to provide the documentation nor why it was delivered piecemeal.

In May 2023, the IRS requested “production related to all 238 research projects” in the sample frame.

⇒ The extent of documentation requested is not clear from the court documents. For example, this “production” information could have merely been ancillary data to verify the representativeness of the sample to the frame – which is a reasonable albeit atypical request. On the other hand, it could have been as much as the four-part test – which hereto now was unheard of. Typically, if there were no

irregularities in the sample selections that rendered a sample unsuitable for unbiased extrapolation, the IRS would audit the taxpayer's sample selections, not the entire sample frame.

PDG then filed a motion for a protective order per Rule 103 that asked to limit discovery to a sample of three to six research projects out of the twenty qualifying projects. In Tax Court, Rule 103 is meant to protect taxpayers from unreasonable requests by the IRS. It states, "On motion by a party or any other affected person, or on the Court's own, and for good cause, the Court may make any order that justice requires to protect a party or other person from annoyance, embarrassment, oppression, or undue burden or expense... If a motion for a protective order is denied in whole or in part, the Court may, on such terms or conditions it deems just, order any party or person to comply or to respond following the procedure involved."^{vii}

The Tax Court denied the motion, reasoning that:

1. Limiting discovery would prevent the IRS from fully assessing the validity of the credits.
 2. The taxpayer bears the burden of proving its entitlement to the credits.
 3. The taxpayer had not "shown that the three to six selected projects were representative of the 238 projects underlying the research credits and would produce statistically valid results."
 4. The narrow scope requested by the taxpayer, with four tax years at issue, "could result in a nonreflective decrease in its tax liability ...".
 5. The IRS's request for details "is reasonably calculated to produce relevant information" regarding the taxpayer's eligibility for the credits.
 6. Without the agreement of both parties, they have previously held that limiting the scope to a sample of research projects is improper because doing so would relieve a taxpayer of his burden of proving entitlement to the research credit (*Betz v. Commissioner*, T.C. Memo. 2023-84, at 77 n.30).
- ⇒ The Court's decision to deny a motion to limit discovery to a tiny subset of a random sample, of course, is based on sound statistical principles.

It is important to note that the Court did not reject sound statistical sampling and estimation, nor did it reject results based on the full sample of 24 projects. Instead, it rejected reliance on only a subset of the sample. It was also unclear whether the subset would be chosen randomly or judgmentally.

Unfortunately, some articles published on the case lead their readers to believe the IRS rejected sampling. It is easy to understand how the incorrect conclusion was decided as many laypeople do not discern between the concepts.

However, the judge also said, "...the Court advises the respondent [IRS] that its continued cooperation and willingness to better streamline this case for trial is expected since it will preserve both judicial resources and resources of the parties."

Ultimately, the IRS and PDG agreed to try the case based on "a non-binding three projects." The Tax Court ruled that none of the three projects passed the four-part test and there the deficiency and penalty stand. However, the three projects were non-binding for extrapolation up to the sampling frame. Therefore, the dispute continues.

Ramesh C. Kapur & Chanda Kapur v. Commissioner of Internal Revenue

Kapur, Kapur & Associates Inc. (KAI), is a civil and environmental engineering firm that designs transportation and remediation systems. Its founder, Ramesh C. Kapur is the chief executive officer, president, and majority shareholder of KAI.

KAI engaged alliantgroup to evaluate a population of 2,000-3,000 projects for the Research Tax Credit. Non-qualifying projects were removed from consideration, and then eligibility for the research credit was determined based on a stratified sample that was extrapolated to the remaining projects in the full sampling frame.

KAI timely filed Forms 1120S, U.S. Income Tax Return for an S Corporation, for the Tax Years 2014-2018. Ramesh C. As married filing jointly, Kapur and his wife, Chanda Kapur claimed flowthrough research credits totaling \$238,958 with respect to KAI's projects on their Forms 1040 U.S. Income Tax Return for Tax Years 2014-2018. (They did not claim research credits with respect to all of KAI's projects.)

The IRS audited the RTC for these tax years and challenged some of the claims, issuing a deficiency of \$186,648 and a Section 6662(a) penalty of \$7,187.

The IRS issued informal discovery requests to the Kapurs - who limited their responses to KAI's two largest projects. They represented that these two projects accounted for over 72% of the claimed QREs.

- ⇒ Like PDG, it is unclear why the IRS did not already have this information from the initial audit for each sampled unit, as that would have been customary.

Formal discovery ensued. In the formal discovery request, like PGG, the IRS requested information regarding “production” for the entire sampling frame, not just the sampled items. In this case, court documents clarified that production meant for each project in the sampling frame, the IRS was asking for a brief description of the project and the qualified research activities that the taxpayer performed for the project. The IRS also requested to interview 16 employees, including Mr. Kapur.

Also, like PDG, the Kapurs requested that only two to four individuals with knowledge of the projects be interviewed, that scope also be limited to two to four projects, and that those projects include the two largest ones. They also replied that the work to fulfill the IRS's request might exceed the \$186,648 credit amount in dispute and argued that discovery related to 2,000—3,000 projects was not proportional to the amount in controversy.

- ⇒ Like PDG's request, this taxpayer request is not statistically sound due to its small sample of a sample covering multiple years. It is unlikely that the approach would even allow for two sample selections per stratum and year, which is the minimum to even be able to calculate confidence intervals around the QRE estimates.

In addition, the largest sampling units typically have larger qualifying rates than smaller ones. In sample designs across a wide variety of applications, large outliers are most commonly isolated into their own strata to avoid small changes in their outcomes from unduly swaying statistical estimates. All of the projects in these strata are reviewed separately to avoid inaccuracies in the estimates.

However, in opposition to the taxpayer's motion for protection, the IRS revealed a (flawed) view that sampling cannot be validly performed in the RTC at all. The reasoning is listed below.

1. “Because representativeness is a threshold requirement for any reliable sample, sampling is not likely to lead to reliable determinations of whether petitioners have met their burden to prove entitlement to the Research Credits.”

2. “The varied and fact intensive determinations that the four-part test requires with respect to each business component ... do not support a finding of a homogenous population to sample reliably.”
 3. “Indeed, petitioners claim in the instant motion that the projects at issue in this case concern 3,001 unique business components - if each project is unique, it is not clear how any of the projects could be representative of the population of projects.”
- ⇒ It is a common misunderstanding among laypeople that sample units must be alike for estimates from a sample to be valid or accurate. Heterogenous populations regularly are sampled to produce highly accurate estimates – they merely require larger samples. The problem with the taxpayer’s request is not precisely that the population is heterogenous. It is that their proposed reduced sample size is ridiculously small for the setting.

The court responded that, “It is common for parties to agree to sampling in lieu of extensive discovery and litigation with respect to each project.” Then it gave examples:

1. The parties agreed at the outset to try a sample that is binding on all projects (*Suder*, T.C. Memo. 2014-201, at 15).
2. The parties agree to try a sample with the expectation that the court’s conclusions will enable them to resolve their differences with respect to the remaining projects (*Little Sandy Coal Co.*, T.C. Memo. 2021-15, at 20—21, *aff’d*, 62 F.4th 287 (7th Cir. 2023)).
3. The parties agreed to sampling, but, since they were unable to agree on a method, the Tax Court selected the sampling methodology (*Tangel*, T.C. Memo. 2021-1).

The Court further commented that in this case, the situation that it faced was unusual, as the IRS rejected sampling completely.

Ultimately, the court denied the taxpayers’ motion and agreed the IRS would not be able to choose a representative sample for discovery if it did not have preliminary information on all projects. Regarding the taxpayer’s argument that the IRS request was disproportionate to the expense, the Tax Court added that the taxpayers could simply limit the credit claim to the projects they wanted in the sample. If they wanted more credit, they would need to be prepared to provide substantiation. Finally, the Court added that KAI could cooperate with the IRS and identify information regarding business components in the sampling frame to convince the Service to agree to a representative sample.

While the court acknowledged precedent supporting the use of sampling, it upheld the IRS position due to insufficient preliminary documentation. As a result, the taxpayer was compelled either to provide comprehensive substantiation or to curtail their credit claims.

Policy and Practical Implications - IRS Form 6765 Revisions Enhanced reporting obligations introduced for tax years 2024–2025.

IRS Form 6765 is necessary to claim the Research Tax Credit. A revised draft version was released in February 2025, with feedback requested by June 2025. The updated form requires significantly more detailed information, like what was requested in the KAI case. In Section G of the form, for the top 80% of QREs or up to 50 business components, taxpayers must report on each component, its type, research goals, expenditures (broken down by category), and QREs (also categorized). According to the directions, the new requirements apply even when statistical sampling is used.

Unfortunately, when sampling is applied, it is impossible to provide the top 80% of the QREs or the top 50 largest business components in the population as measured by their QREs – even if the top 80%/50 business components (as measured by expenses) were included in the sample.

Consider a taxpayer making a good faith effort to follow the new Form 6765 guidance. For the sake of simplicity, suppose this taxpayer only has 50 projects for consideration of the RTC. Now explore two scenarios. In the first, the taxpayer reviews all 50 projects without sampling. In the second, the taxpayer applies sampling techniques in compliance with the IRS Revenue Procedure 2011-42. (If there were only 50 projects, one may wonder why sample at all. This is for illustrative purposes; findings in this illustration would apply to 500 projects, 5,000 projects, or even larger populations.)

Scenario 1, No Sampling

In this hypothetical population, suppose each project is a distinct business component. These are listed and identifiable by the project id number. Figure 2 lists these 50 hypothetical projects and their expenditures. The row number is for convenience of the narrative further below. The top 80% of the projects – as measured by expenditures are highlighted in purple in Figure 2.

However, often the expenditures are easily pared down by eliminating job titles or departments that would be unlikely to qualify. The result of this first rough cut is often referred to as the potential or preliminary QREs (PQREs). The top 80% of the projects by PQREs are highlighted in blue.

Then after more extensive work (including the four-part analysis), the actual QREs are ascertained. Hypothetical final figures for the actual QREs are in the last column in Figure 2. Sometimes the final QREs are the same as the PQREs, often they are a little less and sometimes they are a little more because too much was carved out when determining the PQREs. In compliance with the new Form 6765, these QREs are sorted in descending order and the top 80% of the projects by QREs are listed on the form with the requested information. These are highlighted in green. The highlights go down to Row 15 in the figure.

Without sampling, the process of implementing the new instructions is straightforward. A quick glance shows the top 80%/50 business components in terms of QREs would not necessarily align with the top 80%/50 as measured by expenses or PQREs.

Figure 2: A Hypothetical Population - No Sampling

Row #	Project ID #	Expenditures	PQREs	Actual QREs
1	991	\$10,976,126	\$4,381,862	\$3,345,373
2	931	\$1,416,126	\$436,193	\$441,622
3	996	\$1,229,492	\$347,280	\$363,360
4	455	\$646,407	\$292,721	\$292,721
5	482	\$947,239	\$245,264	\$245,264
6	497	\$824,264	\$236,750	\$236,750
7	133	\$590,487	\$195,580	\$179,593
8	586	\$804,660	\$192,486	\$175,627
9	701	\$155,566	\$151,152	\$155,566
10	729	\$185,940	\$142,656	\$142,656
11	759	\$792,631	\$261,621	\$130,810
12	873	\$542,692	\$119,868	\$119,868
13	213	\$205,374	\$103,574	\$103,574
14	581	\$115,315	\$87,959	\$87,959
15	374	\$150,403	\$74,506	\$81,449
16	4	\$88,670	\$78,419	\$78,419
17	92	\$166,025	\$66,653	\$75,587
18	41	\$127,158	\$86,840	\$72,158
19	943	\$99,207	\$39,603	\$68,318
20	89	\$173,764	\$111,312	\$66,870
21	158	\$172,974	\$90,727	\$61,813
22	722	\$57,731	\$38,741	\$57,731
23	457	\$121,313	\$48,516	\$56,620

Row #	Project ID #	Expenditures	PQREs	Actual QREs
24	786	\$55,857	\$87,431	\$55,857
25	777	\$128,353	\$28,321	\$55,845
26	119	\$54,663	\$45,346	\$54,663
27	534	\$169,444	\$64,154	\$54,454
28	843	\$72,226	\$14,813	\$54,454
29	948	\$123,079	\$69,646	\$51,812
30	798	\$50,831	\$54,499	\$50,831
31	932	\$55,907	\$79,261	\$47,144
32	311	\$182,613	\$72,950	\$44,671
33	932	\$572,042	\$94,274	\$43,031
34	774	\$92,863	\$39,493	\$42,012
35	855	\$102,509	\$40,996	\$40,996
36	434	\$118,294	\$47,316	\$40,798
37	306	\$152,591	\$47,022	\$38,997
38	322	\$155,701	\$70,195	\$36,130
39	601	\$92,540	\$36,877	\$31,407
40	10	\$67,916	\$32,253	\$28,869
41	698	\$104,479	\$7,359	\$27,632
42	64	\$148,841	\$98,263	\$25,585
43	317	\$52,592	\$21,006	\$24,388
44	99	\$77,319	\$30,885	\$23,955
45	506	\$79,295	\$28,899	\$23,141
46	715	\$55,552	\$22,194	\$17,192
47	985	\$199,173	\$68,282	\$15,234
48	177	\$131,404	\$11,489	\$0
49	555	\$67,303	\$26,845	\$0
50	958	\$52,218	\$19,539	\$0
	Total	\$23,805,169	\$9,089,890	\$7,568,806

Scenario 2, Sampling

Now consider the same 50 projects where the taxpayer uses sampling and makes a good faith effort to follow the new Form 6765 instructions as illustrated in Figure 3. The actual QREs are unknown at the time of sampling and will only be known in the sampled selections.

As such, a reasonable taxpayer attempting to capture the top 80% of the QREs post sampling would design their sample around the PQREs because they typically more closely align with the actual QREs than total expenditures.

Suppose this taxpayer takes the top 80% of the PQREs as a “certainty” stratum where all projects are reviewed. This is Stratum 1 in this example. Out of the remaining projects, two more strata are formed according to the size of the PQREs. These are Strata 2 and 3. Random numbers are assigned to each project in some software package and the projects corresponding to the 5 smallest random numbers in each stratum are selected for the sample in each of Strata 2 and 3. (This is a common sample selection method.) The Sample Selection column is equal to “1” in Figure 3 for the projects selected for the sample.

Note that the taxpayer will only know the values of the actual QREs for the sampled projects. These are provided in the Sample QRE Results column in Figure 3. For convenience the actual QREs for

all 50 projects is also provided in the last column of Figure 3, but the numbers are greyed out as a reminder that these figures are unknown to the taxpayer or the IRS except in the sample selections.

Now compare the sample to reality by comparing the last two columns in Figure 3. Which projects should the taxpayer report on Form 6765? The instructions on the form are to report the top 80% of the QREs. However, in this example, two of those top QRE projects in Figure 3 were not in the sample selections. These are found on Rows 18 and 23 and are highlighted in yellow. The taxpayer would not know what to report on these two projects.

True, the taxpayer could sample more than the top 80% of the PQREs to capture some of these larger actual QREs in their sample selections. However, they would never know whether their sample covered the top 80% of actual QREs.

- ⇒ It is not possible for any taxpayer using sampling to know with certainty that they have followed the instructions of the new IRS Form 6765 as those instructions are currently written.

Yet, it is clear the IRS did not intend to prohibit sampling because the instructions specifically address the case when a taxpayer samples.

Figure 3: Hypothetical Population - with Sampling

Row #	Project ID #	Expenditures	PQREs	Stratum	Random Number	Sample Selection	Sample QRE Results	Actual QREs
1	991	\$10,976,126	\$4,381,862	1	0.12415	1	\$3,345,373	\$3,345,373
2	931	\$1,416,126	\$436,193	1	0.00650	1	\$441,622	\$441,622
3	996	\$1,229,492	\$347,280	1	0.38945	1	\$363,360	\$363,360
4	455	\$646,407	\$292,721	1	0.74795	1	\$292,721	\$292,721
5	759	\$792,631	\$261,621	1	0.46614	1	\$130,810	\$130,810
6	482	\$947,239	\$245,264	1	0.26728	1	\$245,264	\$245,264
7	497	\$824,264	\$236,750	1	0.70363	1	\$236,750	\$236,750
8	133	\$590,487	\$195,580	1	0.12378	1	\$179,593	\$179,593
9	586	\$804,660	\$192,486	1	0.23551	1	\$175,627	\$175,627
10	701	\$155,566	\$151,152	1	0.53313	1	\$155,566	\$155,566
11	729	\$185,940	\$142,656	1	0.12156	1	\$142,656	\$142,656
12	873	\$542,692	\$119,868	1	0.60869	1	\$119,868	\$119,868
13	89	\$173,764	\$111,312	1	0.41569	1	\$66,870	\$66,870
14	213	\$205,374	\$103,574	1	0.51631	1	\$103,574	\$103,574
15	64	\$148,841	\$98,263	1	0.95117	1	\$25,585	\$25,585
16	932	\$572,042	\$94,274	2	0.40602			\$43,031
17	158	\$172,974	\$90,727	2	0.20350	1	\$61,813	\$61,813
18	581	\$115,315	\$87,959	2	0.52110			\$87,959
19	786	\$55,857	\$87,431	2	0.08631	1	\$55,857	\$55,857
20	41	\$127,158	\$86,840	2	0.33341			\$72,158
21	932	\$55,907	\$79,261	2	0.27924			\$47,144
22	4	\$88,670	\$78,419	2	0.13736	1	\$78,419	\$78,419
23	374	\$150,403	\$74,506	2	0.61827			\$81,449
24	311	\$182,613	\$72,950	2	0.35456			\$44,671
25	322	\$155,701	\$70,195	2	0.35630			\$36,130
26	948	\$123,079	\$69,646	2	0.52110			\$51,812
27	985	\$199,173	\$68,282	2	0.75597			\$15,234
28	92	\$166,025	\$66,653	2	0.03394	1	\$75,587	\$75,587
29	534	\$169,444	\$64,154	2	0.09961	1	\$54,454	\$54,454
30	798	\$50,831	\$54,499	2	0.47923			\$50,831

Row #	Project ID #	Expenditures	PQREs	Stratum	Random Number	Sample Selection	Sample QRE Results	Actual QREs
31	457	\$121,313	\$48,516	3	0.61870			\$56,620
32	434	\$118,294	\$47,316	3	0.65996			\$40,798
33	306	\$152,591	\$47,022	3	0.96512			\$38,997
34	119	\$54,663	\$45,346	3	0.69530			\$54,663
35	855	\$102,509	\$40,996	3	0.65014			\$40,996
36	943	\$99,207	\$39,603	3	0.11502	1	\$68,318	\$68,318
37	774	\$92,863	\$39,493	3	0.20756	1	\$42,012	\$42,012
38	722	\$57,731	\$38,741	3	0.59627			\$57,731
39	601	\$92,540	\$36,877	3	0.77255			\$31,407
40	10	\$67,916	\$32,253	3	0.66982			\$28,869
41	99	\$77,319	\$30,885	3	0.81988			\$23,955
42	506	\$79,295	\$28,899	3	0.60149			\$23,141
43	777	\$128,353	\$28,321	3	0.49959			\$55,845
44	555	\$67,303	\$26,845	3	0.87295			\$0
45	715	\$55,552	\$22,194	3	0.09680	1	\$17,192	\$17,192
46	317	\$52,592	\$21,006	3	0.73458			\$24,388
47	958	\$52,218	\$19,539	3	0.80160			\$0
48	843	\$72,226	\$14,813	3	0.97269			\$54,454
49	177	\$131,404	\$11,489	3	0.49217	1	\$0	\$0
50	698	\$104,479	\$7,359	3	0.00012	1	\$27,632	\$27,632
Total		\$23,805,169	\$9,089,890				\$6,506,525	\$7,568,806

Professional and Academic Reactions

The American Statistical Association’s Statistical Auditing Interest Group (SAIG) includes statisticians, accountants, economists, computer specialist, and many other professionals from accounting or other service firms, academia, and the IRS. In a conference call, SAIG hosted a forum to discuss the quandary of taxpayer compliance with the new form when statistical sampling is used. In attendance were statisticians and tax experts from accounting firms – large and small, academia, IRS Statistical Sampling Coordinators and IRS authors of the instructions for Form 6765.

Unfortunately, attendees from the IRS could only listen to the concerns and ask clarifying questions regarding the issues raised. IRS participants were not allowed to opine on tax positions, answer questions, nor clarify the instructions.

However, they could ask questions, one of which regarded what made sense statistically to report in place of the current top 80%/50 instructions. While it was difficult to answer without clarity around the end goal of the new form, some participants drew attention back to the sample selections; documentation is collected for the cases selected in the sample and therefore it made sense to report information about the sample selections. Although, it was also noted that there is still the issue that sampling units do not always align with business components. Sometimes it could make sense to report the requested business component information for the business component(s)/part of business component(s)/or collection of business components spanning each sampled unit.

Firms that officially submitted comments by the due date June 30, 2025 were surprised to learn that the IRS finalized the form on June 12, 2025 – 2.5 weeks before the due date. However, on October 1, 2025 the IRS extended the date for mandatory compliance with the new instructions to Tax Year 2026 and announced a new March 31, 2026 to comment on the new form and its instructions.

Conclusions

1. Judicial statistical analysis: courts (understandably!) rejected statistically preposterous taxpayer motions – although not always for exactly the right reasons.

2. Significant audit risks arise when taxpayers do not evidentially link business components to selected sampling units and substantiate their QRE claims with the IRS's RTC four-part test.
3. There is persistent confusion observed between random sampling and judgmental example selections of a sub-sample.
4. Amendments to Form 6765 illustrate a policy shift favoring increased detail over procedural efficiency.
5. Ultimately, bad statistics affect more than the single study or case in Tax Court. Misunderstandings of statistical concepts and lack of clarity in the courtroom, lead to widespread false conclusions such as the IRS will not allow sampling, or a sample cannot be drawn from a heterogeneous population.
6. There are instances where the authors of instructions, IRS auditors, and judges may misunderstand statistical concepts. Ongoing concerns exist regarding communication challenges and potential misinterpretations of statistical methodologies. Increased dialogue and education among statisticians, practitioners, the IRS, and the judiciary would be beneficial, although communication barriers can make exchanges more challenging.
7. Statistical sampling continues to be recognized as a valid and efficient approach, contingent on rigorous design and adequate substantiation.
8. Yet, recent judicial cases and evolving IRS policies may deter the use of sampling, thereby escalating compliance costs.

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